

Induction Generator using Re-Weighted Zero-Attracting Incosh Control with Optimized PI Gain for Power Quality

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Data Availability

Appendix A: *Parameters for Simulation Work*

Induction Generator Parameter: Friction factor: 0.0197, Inertia: 0.305, Mutual inductance: 0.07669 Ω , Number of poles: 4, Power rating (P): 3.73 kW, Rated frequency (f): 50 Hz, Rotor inductance: 0.00252 Ω , Rotor resistance: 0.4791 Ω , Self-excitation capacitance (C_e): 128.9 μ F, Stator inductance: 0.002002 Ω , Stator resistance: 0.3939 Ω , Voltage rating (V_{L-L}): 240V.

Wind Turbine Parameters: Air density (ρ): 1.12 kg/m³, Base power of wind turbine: 4.3/0.9 kW, Base revolution velocity: 0.9 pu, Base wind velocity: 12 m/s, Mechanical power of wind turbine: 4.8 kW, Peak power at base wind velocity: 1 pu, Pitch angle: 0°, Power coefficient C_p(λ, β): 0.48, Radius of wind turbine blade: 1.6 m.

BESS Parameters: Capacity: 7.5Ah, Internal resistance (r_s): 0.05 Ω , Rating: 400V, State of charge (SOC) ranging from 10% to 90%, Type: Lithium-ion

Nonlinear Load: Types of loads: Diode bridge rectifier with a resistance (R) of 30 Ω and an inductance (L) of 100 mH.

Appendix B: *Parameters for proposed control*

Step-size $\rho = 0.048$, constant $\alpha = 0.1$, constant $\lambda = 3 \times 10^{-3}$, positive constant $\varepsilon = 10$.

Appendix C: *Parameters for Test Work*

Generator: three-phase, line-powered, 240 V, nonlinear load: R = 56.08 Ω is the restive load applied to the bride rectifier in series with inductive load (L=100mH).

Battery voltage = 400 V, sampling time (T_s) = 65 μ s, DC bus capacitor (C_{dc}) = 3000 μ F, interface inductor: L_f = 4 mH, passive filter parameter (ripple filter): R_f = 5 Ω , C_f = 20 μ F.

Fig. Hardware setup